

Growth of *Chlorella saccharophila* on wet oxidized manure

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WO of anaerobic digested manure

The anaerobic digested manure was separated using centrifugation and the liquid fraction was separated into 4 fractions, three were wet oxidized at 20 bar O₂

Figure 1: AD manure after separation by centrifugation and wet oxidation, from left to right: No treatment, 170, 210 and 260 °C, respectively.

Figure 2: Light absorption of the control and WO manure. The treatment completely removes light absorbing molecules as phenols. The absorbance is lowered more than 100 times.

Light Absorption The total phenol content decreased from approx 250 [mg/L] to zero when treated at 260 °C.

Composition

Table 1: Composition of the separated WO AD manure. It is seen that complex molecules are broken down and acid concentration rises, especially formic and acetic acid. In general the treatment decreases the mineral concentrations by an average 30%, mainly due to different precipitation products.

Content	0	170	210	260 °C
Dry matter	1,25	0,89	0,62	0,87 %
PH	7,75	7,71	7,22	7,24
Total carbon - TOC	1878	1810	1293	1596 [mg/L]
Total Phenol	254	74	15	-2 [mg/L]
Total N	127	96	79	121 [mM]
Ammonium nitrogen	104	81	73	116 [mM]
Phosphorous	1,61	0,65	0,65	0,65 [mM]
Potassium	54	41	36	56 [mM]
Magnesium	5	2	2	3 [mM]
Cubber	0,01	0,05	0,04	0,03 [mM]
Sulphur	2,81	1,87	1,87	2,81 [mM]
Xylitol	0	57	129	147 [mg/L]
Formic acid	17	394	539	309 [mg/L]
Acetic acid	463	755	1168	1486 [mg/L]
Propionic acid	113	162	193	116 [mg/L]
Succinic acid	0	72	134	197 [mg/L]
Glycolic acid	0	103	172	341 [mg/L]
Formic acid	10	403	489	326 [mg/L]

Abstract

The aim of this study was to investigate the effect of wet oxidation (WO) on anaerobic digested (AD) cow manure and evaluate it as a phototrophic growth medium for phototrophic microalgae. The medium supported growth without addition of other components, and the highest growth rate was found to be 0,74 day⁻¹ with a concentration of 7% WO AD manure, compared to an average of 0,61 day⁻¹ on standard minimal medium. At concentrations of 15% or above growth was inhibited. The results shows that WO AD manure can be used as a nutrient source for phototrophic fermentations, but calculations shows that to achieve high biomass concentration medium composition and preparation needs to be optimized to better fit the algae biomass composition or a continuous feeding strategy should be applied.

Growth of *C. saccharophila* on manure

Method Growth was evaluated using the freshwater micro algae *Chlorella saccharophila*. The specific setup was designed for these experiments. The algae was grown in 50 ml shake flasks with a working volume of 25 ml, on a magnetic stirrer with a small magnet and 250-300 rpm. The light was supplied by 4 60W fluorescent tubes. The light intensity was measured to 130-140 [μmol photons m⁻² s⁻¹] The temperature in the lab was 22-24 °C, and a fan was used to avoid local heating by the light tubes. Cultures were checked for contamination in microscope. Growth was measured by spectrophotometer at 600 nm.

Experimental Setup The growth evaluation was done by growth rate estimation based on linear regression of LN(OD). Only single samples were run. Control on std. medium was run with every experiment and in total 5 times. The following screening were done for all conditions:

- 0,5% 2% and 5% manure and std. medium as a toxicity test.
- 7% manure without std. medium but with phosphate buffer, to test for phosphate limitation.
- 15% and 25% manure, no P-buffer or std medium added.

Results See the growth rates in table 2. Approximately equal growth was seen for concentrations of all temperature treatments up to 7% WO AD cow manure. Heterotrophic growth could not be detected for concentrations below 15%. Phosphate was calculated as limiting substrate but, addition of phosphate buffer did not improve the maximum growth rate

Table 2: Growth rate [day⁻¹] of *C. Saccharophila*, control and with different concentrations of WO manure. M: WO manure added to std. Medium. P: including Phosphate buffer. Ph: phototrophic growth after. H: Heterotrophic growth on acids from WO.

Conc	Raw	170	210	260	
0,50%	0,55	0,53	0,43	0,53	X
2%	0,43	0,65	0,65	0,74	X
7%	0,23	0,67	0,70	0,67	P
15%	0	0,89	0,65	0	H
15%	0	0,05	0,02	0	Ph
25%	0	0,34	0,38	0	H
25%	0	0	0	0	Ph
control	0,61	+ 0,13 (SD) 5 values			
Avg. 2%,7%	0,66	+ 0,036 (SD) 6 values			

Table 3: Comparison of the elemental composition of the microalgae *Chlorella* with the average elemental composition of the WO AD manure. The theoretical yield of biomass based on a 7% WO AD manure is indicated. [1] n.a. = not analyzed.

Elemental component	content in DW [weight %]	7% WO manure [mg/L]	Supported DW [mg/L]
Carbon	62	1645	2652
Oxygen	20	n.a.	-
Hydrogen	8,5	n.a.	-
Nitrogen	7,0	96,8	1393
Phosphorus	1,5	1,4	93
Potassium	1,2	121,3	9825
Magnesium	0,58	4,0	684
Sulfur	0,34	4,9	1463
Iron	0,30	n.a.	-
Calcium	0,043	n.a.	-
Zinc	0,0028	n.a.	-
Copper	0,0025	0,2	7187
Manganese	0,0060	n.a.	-

Conclusions

In the present study the growth characteristics of the micro algae *Chlorella saccharophila* was investigated when cultivated with different concentrations of WO anaerobic digested manure, treated at 170, 210 and 260 °C respectively. The following conclusions can be drawn

Wet oxidation of manure

- The WO successfully removed the malodor from the manure.
- The WO could degrade phenols completely from the medium, resulting in a clear medium that allowed light to penetrate and thus be suitable for phototrophic growth.

- The WO resulted in a decreased toxicity of the AD manure.

Algae Growth on WO manure

- The WO manure could completely replace defined growth medium, and equivalent growth or better was seen with WO manure concentrations from 0,5 to 7%
- At concentrations of 15% equivalent or better growth rates was seen for heterotrophic growth on the produced acetic- and formic acid, but phototrophic growth was inhibited.
- At a concentration of 25% WO manure, decrease in heterotrophic growth was seen and completely inhibition under phototrophic growth. Indicating an inhibition of the photosynthetic apparatus.

Future design of a sustainable algae medium

Acknowledgements I express my gratitude to my supervisors, fellow students and all the technicians that have helped me in the laboratory and used time discussing the project with me. The present medium shows potential in batch cultivations up to 7%, but phosphate supplements are needed to increase biomass concentrations above approx. 0,1 [g/L].

References

- Medium preparation based on the here shown method needs to be optimized to increase the phosphate content. During solid liquid

separation only an average 20% of the phosphate stays in the liquid phase, while it is 86% of the total nitrogen [2].

- Iron content of the AD-manure needs to be studied, as iron is an important co-factor in the photosynthetic system.
- DW needs to be studied to verify theoretical values.
- A continuous or fed-batch feeding strategy should be applied to avoid

